

Original Research

Political Connections as a Moderator in the Profitability, Leverage and Financial Distress Relationship: Evidence from the Jakarta Islamic Index

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Abstract

This study investigates the moderating role of political connections in the relationship between profitability, leverage, and financial distress among companies listed on the Jakarta Islamic Index (JII) from 2019 to 2023. Grounded in Agency Theory and Signaling Theory, the research explores whether political affiliations alter the financial risk profile of firms. A quantitative approach is used, with 74 firm-year observations analyzed through Structural Equation Modeling using Partial Least Squares (SEM-PLS). Financial distress is measured using the Altman Z"-score, while profitability (ROA), leverage (DAR), and political connection (dummy variable) serve as the main predictors. The findings reveal that profitability does not significantly affect financial distress, whereas leverage shows a strong positive effect. Political connections also increase the likelihood of financial distress and significantly strengthen the relationship between leverage and financial distress, though they do not moderate the profitability–distress link. The results contribute to the literature by illustrating how political ties can amplify financial risk, supporting the theoretical insights of Agency Theory and Signaling Theory. These insights are particularly relevant for stakeholders in emerging markets seeking to manage governance and financial vulnerabilities.

Keywords: Financial distress, leverage, political connection, profitability.

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Introduction

Over the past five years, Indonesia's economy has faced significant challenges, including the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic, geopolitical tensions, currency depreciation, and political uncertainty surrounding election cycles. These factors have disrupted financial markets and business performance, contributing to an increase in corporate delistings from the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX). Between 2019 and 2024, 15 companies were officially delisted, and 41 others were reported to be at high risk of delisting due to prolonged financial distress (Tonce, 2024). The Jakarta Islamic Index (JII), which comprises the most liquid Sharia-compliant stocks, has also experienced consecutive negative returns, such as -9.69% in 2020 and -8.9% in 2023. This signals the growing financial vulnerability of firms within the index.

Financial distress—commonly defined as a condition where firms struggle to meet their financial obligations—poses a serious risk to corporate sustainability and stakeholder interests. Two core financial indicators often associated with distress are profitability and leverage. However, empirical findings on how these variables affect financial distress remain inconclusive. Some studies suggest that higher profitability reduces distress risk (Diyanto, 2020; Rahmawati *et al.*, 2023), while others find no significant relationship or even a positive association (Haris *et al.*, 2022; Purwanti, 2022).

Similarly, while leverage is generally linked to higher financial risk (Mahaningrum & Merkusiwati, 2020), recent research also reports mixed outcomes (Luspratama *et al.*, 2023; Yazdanfar & Öhman, 2020). This inconsistency reflects a research gap regarding the conditions under which profitability and leverage affect distress and whether contextual factors shape these relationships.

This study addresses that gap by introducing political connection as a potential moderating factor. In emerging markets like Indonesia, political affiliations often influence corporate governance, financing decisions, and access to resources. The impact is particularly pronounced in Indonesia's state-owned enterprises (SOEs), where political appointments surged under President Joko Widodo's second term, increasing by 400%—from just 3 appointments in his first term to 15 in the second. High-profile cases include Grace Natalie's appointment at MIND ID and Simon Aloysius Mantiri's at Pertamina (Transparency International, 2024). These trends highlight the institutionalization of political influence in corporate structures.

Prior studies have shown that politically connected firms may either benefit from preferential treatment or suffer from agency-related inefficiencies (Faccio, 2006; Kalbuana *et al.*, 2022). By examining political connections as a moderator, this study seeks to extend Agency Theory—which highlights conflicts of interest and misaligned incentives—and enrich Signaling Theory, by evaluating how political ties alter the interpretation of profitability and leverage as financial signals.

This study aims to examine how profitability and leverage influence financial distress among firms listed on the Jakarta Islamic Index and to assess whether political connections moderate these relationships. By introducing political affiliation as a contextual factor, this research deepens the application of Agency Theory and Signaling

Theory, offering new insights into how internal financial metrics interact with external institutional influences in emerging market settings.

Theoretical Framework

Agency Theory

Agency Theory, as proposed by Jensen & Meckling (1976), emphasizes the contractual relationship between principals (owners or shareholders) and agents (managers). In this relationship, agents are entrusted to act on behalf of the principals but often pursue their own interests, leading to agency conflicts. This problem is exacerbated by information asymmetry, where agents have more detailed knowledge about the company than principals. In the context of financial distress, this asymmetry can result in managers prioritizing short-term benefits, such as higher compensation, over long-term financial stability (Kalbuana *et al.*, 2022; Tiara *et al.*, 2024).

Political connection intensifies agency conflicts. For example, politically connected individuals in state-owned enterprises (SOEs) often prioritize political agendas over shareholder value. This misalignment may lead to inefficient allocation of resources or high agency costs, such as funds diverted for political gains, increasing the risk of financial distress (Nuswantara *et al.*, 2023). Additionally, politically connected firms may take on excessive leverage due to perceived access to preferential financing, further exacerbating financial instability (Bertrand *et al.*, 2018; Faccio, 2006). The application of Agency Theory in this study explains how political connections influence the relationship between profitability and leverage with financial distress. Specifically, political connections may weaken the protective effect of profitability and amplify the risks associated with high leverage.

Signaling Theory

Signaling Theory, introduced by Spence (1973), emphasizes the role of observable signals in conveying information about an entity's internal conditions to external stakeholders. In the context of corporate finance, profitability and leverage serve as critical signals of a company's likelihood of experiencing financial distress (Amah & Sudrajat, 2023). Profitability is often interpreted as a positive signal of financial stability. High profitability indicates operational efficiency and the ability to generate sufficient income to cover financial obligations. However, low profitability can signal inefficiencies in asset utilization and an increased risk of financial distress. On the other hand, leverage typically acts as a negative signal. High leverage reflects a heavy reliance on debt financing, which increases financial risk, especially when revenues are insufficient to meet interest and principal payments. Companies with high leverage are perceived as being at greater risk of financial distress due to the increased burden of financial obligations.

Political connections add complexity to these signals. While political ties might initially signal enhanced access to government support or favorable regulatory conditions, they can also act as a warning signal of potential governance inefficiencies or resource mismanagement. For instance, the dramatic rise in politically connected appointments in

Indonesian SOEs has raised questions about decision-making quality and its impact on financial stability. In this study, profitability and leverage are treated as signals of financial distress, and political connections are analyzed for their role in altering stakeholder interpretations of these financial indicators.

Despite the theoretical expectations proposed by Agency Theory and Signaling Theory, empirical findings on the relationship between profitability, leverage, and financial distress have been inconsistent. Some studies report that higher profitability reduces financial distress due to stronger internal financing and operational efficiency (Diyanto, 2020; Rahmawati *et al.*, 2023), yet others find no significant relationship—particularly in volatile environments such as during the COVID-19 pandemic (Haris *et al.*, 2022). Similarly, while leverage is generally associated with a higher risk of distress (Mahaningrum & Merkusiwati, 2020), other findings indicate that this effect can be neutral or insignificant, depending on firm-specific conditions and industry context (Luspratama *et al.*, 2023). These variations may arise from differences in economic periods, sample sizes, sectoral focus, and the financial ratios or models used. As such, it is important to reexamine these relationships within a more specific institutional setting. This study does so by focusing on Sharia-compliant firms listed on the Jakarta Islamic Index (JII) and incorporating political connections as a moderating variable to better understand how institutional dynamics shape the influence of profitability and leverage on financial distress.

Hypothesis Development

Agency Theory posits that conflicts between managers and shareholders can lead to decisions that increase a firm's risk of financial distress. Signaling Theory adds that financial indicators such as profitability and leverage serve as signals to the market about a firm's stability. Building on these theories, this study proposes five hypotheses to examine the direct and moderating effects of financial indicators and political connections on financial distress.

The role of profitability in financial distress

Several empirical studies suggest that higher profitability enables firms to better manage operational costs, service debt, and withstand external shocks, thereby reducing the likelihood of financial distress (Diyanto, 2020; ElBannan, 2021; Rahmawati *et al.*, 2023). These findings align with the signaling perspective, where strong financial performance signals lower risk. Based on this, the first hypothesis is formulated as:

H₁: Profitability negatively affects financial distress.

The impact of leverage on financial distress

Leverage is widely regarded as a key driver of financial distress due to the burden of fixed interest obligations. Empirical findings consistently show a positive association between leverage and financial distress, particularly in emerging markets and capital-intensive industries (Alter & Elekdag, 2020; Mahaningrum & Merkusiwati, 2020;

Rahmawati *et al.*, 2023). Excessive debt can amplify financial fragility, especially under adverse macroeconomic conditions. Therefore:

H₂: Leverage positively affects financial distress.

The influence of political connection on financial distress

Political connection refers to the relationship between a company and political figures or entities, such as government officials or legislators. While political connections may offer benefits like easier access to financing or preferential treatment, Agency Theory highlights the potential conflicts of interest these relationships create. Managers or directors with political affiliations may prioritize political agendas over corporate performance, leading to inefficiencies and increased financial risks. Studies by Faccio (2006) and Bertrand *et al.* (2018) demonstrate that political connections often exacerbate agency costs, contributing to financial distress. Based on this view:

H₃: Political connection positively affects financial distress.

The moderating role of political connection in the profitability-financial distress relationship

Profitability typically reduces financial distress by providing sufficient income to meet obligations. However, political connections may undermine this effect. According to Agency Theory, politically connected managers may divert resources for political purposes, reducing the effectiveness of profitability in mitigating financial distress. Bertrand *et al.* (2018) and Faccio (2006) found that political connections often result in higher agency costs, which dilute the protective impact of profitability. Thus:

H₄: Political connection weakens the negative relationship between profitability and financial distress.

The moderating role of political connection in the leverage-financial distress relationship

Leverage increases financial risk due to higher repayment obligations. Political connections may amplify this risk, as they encourage companies to over-rely on debt, expecting preferential treatment or government bailouts. Agency Theory explains that political connections can lead to inefficient use of debt for non-productive purposes, further exacerbating financial instability. Studies by Belghitar *et al.* (2019) and Halford & Li (2020) support the notion that politically connected firms are more likely to leverage debt excessively, increasing the likelihood of financial distress. Accordingly:

H₅: Political connection strengthens the positive relationship between leverage and financial distress.

The conceptual model of this research is shown in the the Fig. 1 below.

Figure 1. Conceptual Model

Methodology

Sample Selection and Data Selection

This study adopts a quantitative approach using a causal-comparative design to examine the relationships between profitability, leverage, political connection, and financial distress. The analysis employs Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM), which is particularly suited for predictive research involving complex models with interaction effects and is robust to violations of normality and small sample sizes. The data analysis was conducted using SmartPLS 4.0.

The population consists of companies listed on the Jakarta Islamic Index (JII) over a five-year period from 2019 to 2023. A purposive sampling technique was applied to select firms that met specific criteria, including the availability of complete financial reports and clear identification of political connections among board members, commissioners, or executives. Based on these criteria, a total of 42 companies were included in the study, resulting in 76 firm-year observations that formed the final dataset. The financial and governance data were sourced from annual reports, financial statements, and company disclosures publicly available through the Indonesia Stock Exchange and corporate websites.

PLS-SEM was selected over covariance-based SEM (CB-SEM) due to its suitability for predictive modeling, its tolerance for non-normal data distributions, and its effectiveness in estimating complex models that include moderating variables (Chin, 2009). This method is particularly appropriate for studies with relatively small samples and exploratory research objectives, such as assessing the influence of political connections in the context of Islamic-indexed firms in Indonesia.

The structural model was evaluated through several quality assessment criteria. Convergent validity was tested using Average Variance Extracted (AVE), and internal consistency was evaluated using Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability (CR), all of which met recommended thresholds. Discriminant validity was assessed using the Fornell-Larcker criterion (Haryono, 2016).

Multicollinearity was examined using the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF), with all variables falling below the recommended threshold of 5, indicating no multicollinearity concern. Since PLS-SEM is non-parametric, it does not require assumptions of homoscedasticity or address endogeneity in the same way as covariance-based techniques. Nonetheless, the model's explanatory power was analyzed using R² values, and the strength of the relationships was assessed through path coefficients and their significance levels. The structural equations formulated for this research are as follows:

$$FDS_{it} = \alpha + \beta_1 ROA_{it} + \beta_2 DAR_{it} + \beta_3 PCO_{it} + \beta_4 (ROA_{it} \times PCO_{it}) + \beta_5 (DAR_{it} \times PCO_{it}) + e$$

where:

FDS	Dependent variable, representing financial distress
α	Constant (intercept)
β_1 and β_2	Regression coefficients for the independent variables
ROA	Independent variable, representing profitability
DAR	Independent variable, representing leverage
β_3	Regression coefficient for the moderating variable, political connection
PCO	Moderating variable, representing political connection
β_4	Regression coefficient for the interaction between ROA and PCO
$ROA_{it} \times PCO_{it}$	Interaction term between profitability (ROA) and political connection (PCO)
β_5	Regression coefficient for the interaction between DAR and PCO
$DAR_{it} \times PCO_{it}$	Interaction term between leverage (DAR) and political connection (PCO)

Variable Measurement

This study's independent variables include profitability (ROA) and leverage (DAR), which were derived from the annual financial reports of companies listed in the Jakarta Islamic Index (JII) on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX) for the 2019–2023 period. The dependent variable, financial distress, is measured using the Altman Z''-score modified model. The moderating variable, political connection, is operationalized as a dummy variable. The measurement methods for each variable are as follows:

- Financial Distress (FDS): measured using the Altman Z''-score formula:

$$Z'' = 6,56X_1 + 3,26X_2 + 6,72X_3 + 1,05X_4$$

- Profitability (ROA): measured as the ratio of net income to total assets:

$$\text{Return on Assets} = \frac{\text{Net Income}}{\text{Total Assets}}$$

- Leverage (DAR): measured as the ratio of total debt to total assets:

$$\text{Debt to Asset Ratio} = \frac{\text{Total Debt}}{\text{Total Assets}}$$

- **Political Connection (PCO):** measured as a dummy variable, where a value of 1 indicates the presence of political connections, such as board members or executives with political affiliations, and a value of 0 indicates the absence of political connections.

Findings

Descriptive Statistic

Based on the results of the data processed, the results of descriptive statistical analysis are as follows:

Table 1. Descriptive Statistic of Data

	FDS	ROA	DAR	PCO
Mean	3.491	0.072	0.450	0.592
Median	3.039	0.055	0.445	1.000
Maximum	8.092	0.358	0.908	1.000
Minimum	-0.297	-0.138	0.101	0.000
Std. Dev.	1.964	0.086	0.203	0.494
Skewness	0.401	1.406	0.177	-0.382
Kurtosis	-0.225	2.821	-0.816	-1.904

Table 1 presents the descriptive statistics for the key variables: Financial Distress (FDS), Profitability (ROA), Leverage (DAR), and Political Connection (PCO). The mean value of FDS is 3.491, with a minimum of -0.297 and a maximum of 8.092, indicating variations in the financial stability of firms. ROA has a mean of 0.072, reflecting low average profitability, while its range, from -0.138 to 0.358, shows that some firms experienced losses. DAR has a mean of 0.450, indicating that firms on average finance 45% of their assets through debt. For PCO, the mean value of 0.592 suggests that 59.2% of firms are politically connected, with a standard deviation of 0.494 indicating moderate variability.

Partial Least Square

Structural Model Test (Inner Model Test)

To determine the relationships between the constructs, as well as the significance values and R-squared of the research model, an inner model test was conducted. The R-squared values for endogenous constructs and path coefficients for exogenous constructs were analyzed using PLS to evaluate the structural model. The model's relevance was further assessed through the t-statistic values. Figure 2 illustrates the structural model used in this study.

Figure 2. Structural Model Output

R-square Test

Table 2. R-square Test Result

	R-square	R-square adjusted
FDS	0.896	0.889

Based on the R-square test results presented in Table 2, the financial distress variable (FDS) has an R-square value of 0.896. This indicates that 89.6% of the variation in financial distress can be explained by the independent variables, including profitability (ROA), leverage (DAR), and the moderating variable, political connection (PCO). The remaining 10.4% of the variation is influenced by other factors not included in this study. The adjusted R-square value of 0.889 further confirms the model's robustness in explaining the dependent variable.

Hypothesis Test

Table 3. Path Coefficient Test

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation	T-statistics (O/STDEV)	P-values
DAR -> FDS	0.707	0.711	0.103	6.888	0.000
PCO -> FDS	0.152	0.152	0.085	1.797	0.036
ROA -> FDS	0.062	0.067	0.074	0.842	0.200
PCO x ROA -> FDS	0.069	0.061	0.091	0.758	0.224
PCO x DAR -> FDS	0.305	0.303	0.121	2.529	0.006

This study tested five hypotheses using PLS-SEM on 76 firm-year observations of companies listed on the Jakarta Islamic Index (JII) from 2019 to 2023. The model's explanatory power is strong, with an R² value of 0.896 for financial distress, indicating

that approximately 90% of the variance is explained by the predictor variables and their interactions. The results and their implications are discussed below.

The path analysis shows that profitability (ROA) does not significantly affect financial distress (coefficient = 0.062; $p = 0.200$). While the manuscript initially attributes this to COVID-19 disruptions, alternative explanations warrant consideration. For example, the narrow distribution of ROA values among the sample firms may weaken its predictive power. Additionally, profitability may not directly signal risk in politically influenced or Sharia-compliant firms, where other non-financial factors (e.g., compliance or moral hazard) may play a stronger role. This finding is consistent with Haris *et al.* (2022) and Purwanti (2022), who reported similar non-significant relationships in high-uncertainty environments. Therefore, H1 is rejected.

Leverage (DAR) has a strong, positive, and significant effect on financial distress (coefficient = 0.707; $p = 0.000$), supporting H2. This finding aligns with prior studies such as Mahaningrum & Merkusiwati (2020) and Rahmawati *et al.* (2023). Importantly, the effect size is economically meaningful—a 0.1 increase in the debt-to-asset ratio could potentially lead to a 7% rise in financial distress scores. This emphasizes the critical role of capital structure decisions in shaping corporate vulnerability, especially in markets with weaker governance mechanisms or higher debt dependence.

Political connection (PCO) shows a significant and positive direct effect on financial distress (coefficient = 0.152; $p = 0.036$), thus supporting H3. This supports Agency Theory, where politically connected firms may pursue riskier strategies, anticipating government protection or preferential treatment. The result also aligns with Faccio (2006) and Kalbuana *et al.* (2022), who found that political ties can increase agency conflicts and reduce market discipline.

The interaction between political connection and profitability is not significant (coefficient = 0.069; $p = 0.308$), leading to the rejection of H4. This suggests that political ties do not alter how profitability relates to distress. One possible explanation is that profitability is an internally driven performance metric, less susceptible to external interventions. Political ties may influence perceptions or access to external resources, but are unlikely to compensate for poor operational performance. This finding mirrors Nuswantara *et al.* (2023), who also observed no significant moderation in this path.

In contrast, political connection significantly moderates the relationship between leverage and financial distress (coefficient = 0.305; $p = 0.006$), supporting H5. The result indicates that political ties amplify the negative consequences of high leverage. This can be interpreted through Agency Theory, as firms with political backing may be emboldened to accumulate more debt due to perceived institutional safety nets, reduced creditor scrutiny, or favorable regulation. As a result, politically connected firms with high leverage may face higher financial risk than non-connected firms at similar debt levels.

Conclusion and Discussion

This study examines the influence of profitability and leverage on financial distress, along with the moderating role of political connections, based on 76 firm-year observations from companies listed on the Jakarta Islamic Index (JII) between 2019 and 2023. The analysis was conducted using Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM), with interpretations grounded in Agency Theory and Signaling Theory to better understand corporate financial vulnerability in emerging markets.

The analysis reveals that profitability (ROA) does not have a statistically significant effect on financial distress (coefficient = 0.062; $p = 0.200$). This finding does not support H1, indicating that a firm's internal performance alone may not be sufficient to mitigate financial distress—particularly during the COVID-19 pandemic, which disrupted business fundamentals. From a signaling perspective, profitability may have lost credibility as an indicator of stability in such uncertain times. This result is consistent with prior studies by Haris *et al.* (2022) and Sinambela & Marpaung (2019), which similarly found that profitability had limited predictive power during macroeconomic instability.

The results demonstrate a significant positive relationship between leverage (DAR) and financial distress (coefficient = 0.707; $p = 0.000$), supporting H2. This aligns with Signaling Theory, which holds that high leverage sends adverse signals to the market about a firm's solvency. The effect size suggests that even marginal increases in debt can lead to considerable distress risk. These findings reinforce earlier conclusions by Mahaningrum & Merkusiwati (2020) and Rahmawati *et al.* (2023), both of whom emphasized leverage as a dominant predictor of corporate financial instability.

The analysis confirms a positive and statistically significant relationship between political connection (PCO) and financial distress (coefficient = 0.152; $p = 0.036$), lending empirical support to H3. From the perspective of Agency Theory, this may be attributed to increased agency costs, such as misaligned incentives, weak oversight, or decisions based on political rather than economic rationale. This outcome echoes the findings of Bertrand *et al.* (2018) and Kalbuana *et al.* (2022), who identified similar risks stemming from political affiliations.

The interaction between political connection and profitability does not exhibit a significant effect on financial distress (coefficient = 0.069; $p = 0.308$), offering no empirical support for H4. This indicates that political affiliations do not meaningfully influence the strength or direction of the relationship between profitability and distress. Theoretically, this result reflects a distinction between internal operational efficiency (profitability) and external political influence. It is consistent with the findings of Nuswantara *et al.* (2023), who also observed limited moderating effects in this context.

In contrast, political connection is found to significantly moderate the relationship between leverage and financial distress (coefficient = 0.305; $p = 0.006$), providing empirical support for H5. This implies that politically connected firms may be more susceptible to distress when they are highly leveraged, potentially due to overconfidence, moral hazard, or perceived political protection. These findings are in line with Agency

Theory, and they corroborate the results of Belghitar *et al.* (2019), who concluded that political ties often intensify the financial vulnerabilities associated with excessive debt.

Limitations

Several limitations must be acknowledged. First, the study focuses solely on firms listed on the Jakarta Islamic Index (JII), which may limit generalizability to other sectors or conventional indices. Second, political connections are operationalized as a binary dummy variable, which does not capture variations in the intensity, level (local vs. national), or strategic relevance of those connections. Finally, the five-year study period includes the COVID-19 pandemic, which may distort normal economic behavior.

Recommendations

Future studies may expand the scope by including broader indices such as LQ45, IDX30, or ISSI, or compare Islamic and non-Islamic firms. A more granular approach to measuring political connection—such as the number of politicians involved, their positions, or the nature of the affiliation—could provide deeper insights. Cross-country studies within ASEAN or other emerging markets could explore institutional differences. Alternative financial distress proxies (e.g., Zmijewski or Springate scores) and other moderators, such as board diversity, institutional ownership, or governance quality, may further enrich the model.

For corporate managers, the findings highlight the critical need for prudent leverage management, especially for firms with political affiliations. Over-reliance on debt—combined with political exposure—may substantially increase financial instability. Board appointments should be carefully considered to avoid agency conflicts introduced by politically connected individuals. For investors, the combined presence of high leverage and political connection should be viewed as a red flag when evaluating firm risk. Such firms may require more stringent due diligence and risk assessment. For policymakers, these results underline the importance of strengthening disclosure and governance regulations for politically affiliated firms, particularly regarding debt oversight and transparency. Enhancing regulatory neutrality in financing access could reduce the systemic risk posed by politicized business structures.

Author Contributions

Abida Massi Armand Led the conceptualization and design of the research, conducted the majority of the data analysis, and wrote the initial and final drafts of the manuscript. Additionally, Abida was responsible for overseeing the research process and managing communication with the journal.

Najmudin Najmudin Provided significant support in data collection and contributed to refining the methodology. Najmudin also reviewed and revised the manuscript critically for important intellectual content and ensured the accuracy of the references.

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